

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Bridge Construction Using Cement and Steel Produced with CCS Technology

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

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Image courtesy: Lake Pontchartrain Causeway bridge, [Mark Runde](#)

About this document:

This document provides a possible approach to incorporating Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technology in the production of cement for bridge construction, encapsulated in the construct of 'Neutral Solution Packages' (NSP). Maintaining the 'Neutral' descriptor, these solutions are universally applicable, transcending the limitations of specific geographic sites. The 'Solution' signifies a strategic and effective response to these challenges. 'Packages' represents the all-inclusive nature of these solutions. Designed for stakeholders in urban development, particularly those involved in public infrastructure projects, this document aims to address the process and benefits of using lower fossil emission cement in bridge construction, thus contributing to the reduction of carbon emissions in urban development projects.

Description:

This NSP demonstrates the balance between the added costs associated with the implementation of CCS and the environmental benefits achieved, particularly in terms of the reduction in CO₂ emissions. The focus is on assessing how CCS, when applied to the production of key construction materials such as cement and steel, contributes to the final product, the constructed bridge. Understanding the impact on the costs carried by the end user is crucial, especially for public procurement in cities and municipalities.

Challenge/Goal:

Given the growing focus on corporate carbon footprint, the steel and cement production sectors face a significant hurdle in minimising their CO₂ emissions, particularly within the cement and steel industries. The incorporation of CCS technology into cement and steel plants has the potential to increase overall production expenses of raw materials. Manufacturers may hesitate to adopt CCS in their industrial processes due to concerns about potential economic consequences, decreased competitiveness of the product, and increased production costs

Solution:

With the use of low-carbon products, the overall reduction in CO₂ emissions can be achieved from the end user perspective. Low-emission materials can be a baseline for environmental performance for the construction industry and can have a minimal cost impact on end-users. The construction of a bridge made from products originating from a plant with implemented CCS can contribute to a large reduction in overall carbon emissions, utilising low-carbon cement and steel. The increase in the cost of bridge construction may be cost-effective for reduction in carbon emissions. To fully understand the possible effects of CCS adoption on end users, the costs and CO₂ intensity of relevant products must be evaluated.

Technology components:

Image courtesy : [Subraveti, S. G. et al. 2023](#)

Barriers to development:

Despite its promising potential, CCS faces significant hurdles to widespread adoption, including high costs, technical complexity, limited large-scale demonstrations, and insufficient financial incentives, and, as demonstrated in this NSP, bias toward expected high costs for the end-user and competitive place of products produced with CCS. In their study, Subraveti et al. have shown that using cement and steel produced from CCS equipped facilities in the construction of a bridge could lead to a 51% reduction of the greenhouse emissions associated with the bridge construction for a mere increase of construction cost of 1% (Subraveti, S. G. et al. 2023). Further results from ACCSESS project research show, similar conclusions: even though the costs for producing basic commodities can increase significantly (200% for cement, 75% for pulp, 230% for heat, and 6–37% for refinery products) when implementing CCS, the

increase in prices for end-users would be marginal (1% for railway, 3% for disposable baby diaper, 1% for housing, 0.4% for truck transport and 2% for airfreight). This leaves the basic commodity producer with the greatest risk when investing in high-cost abatement measures such as CCS and represents an additional barrier to the implementation of the technology (Emanuelsson, A.H., Johnsson, F., 2023).

Overcoming these barriers requires concerted efforts in research and development, technological advancements, and supportive policy frameworks that not only encourage CCS implementation, but also emphasise a comprehensive understanding of its impact beyond the plant and towards the end-user, as well as public visibility and demonstration of research findings. Cross-value chain collaboration and long-term agreements are necessary measures to distribute risk across actors throughout the whole value chain.

Enablers to development:

Enablers for the development of this case include the following factors: technological advances that optimise capture processes, reduce energy consumption, and improve cost effectiveness. Supportive policy frameworks with clear regulations, financial incentives, and public awareness campaigns can also drive the adoption of CCS. Industry collaboration, knowledge sharing, and pilot projects can provide valuable insight and demonstrate the feasibility of the technology.

Lessons learnt/ Impact:

- With the incorporation of CCS, despite a marginal 1% increase in overall costs of the end product, a substantial 51% reduction in CO₂ emissions could be achieved.
- The employment of comprehensive life cycle assessments to not only evaluate the overall environmental impact of CCS projects but also to discern the broader effects downstream of the plant where CCS is implemented identifies opportunities for optimisation.
- Encourage supportive regulatory frameworks, streamlined permitting processes, and financial incentives to promote the adoption of CCS in bridge construction.
- Open communication and results demonstration of results may lead to faster technology uptake.

Citizen Engagement and City-Company Collaboration:

- Prioritising transparency and open communication: Establish clear and consistent communication channels to keep citizens informed about the progress, potential impacts, and mitigation measures of the project.
- Public Education and Awareness: Provide thorough public education initiatives to inform the public about CCS technology, its advantages, and its drawbacks.

Addressed SDGs:

Media files and further reading:

Title	Author	Year	Link
Toward an improved cost evaluation of carbon capture and Storage from industry	Roussanaly et al.	2021	ELSEVIER – Cost evaluation of CCS from industry
Is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Really So Expensive? An Analysis of Cascading Costs and CO ₂ Emissions Reduction of Industrial CCS Implementation on the Construction of a Bridge	Subraveti et al.	2023	ACSPublications
20 years of carbon capture and storage	IEA	2016	IEA – CCS
Public perception and acceptance of CCUS: preliminary findings of a qualitative case study in Greece	Stavrianakis et al.	2023	EuropeanComission
The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage – A Product Value Chain Analysis	Anna Hörbe Emanuelsson, Filip Johnsson	2023	The Cost to Consumers of Carbon Capture and Storage—A Product Value Chain Analysis (chalmers.se)
Is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Really So Expensive? An Analysis of Cascading Costs and CO ₂ Emissions Reduction of Industrial CCS Implementation on the Construction of a Bridge	Sai Gokul Subraveti, Elda Rodríguez Angel, Andrea Ramírez, Simon Roussanaly	2023	Is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) Really So Expensive? An Analysis of Cascading Costs and CO₂ Emissions Reduction of Industrial CCS Implementation on the Construction of a Bridge Environmental Science & Technology (acs.org)

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A Product Value Chain Analysis. *Energies*. 16(20):7113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16207113>